

The ATLAS Inner Detector tracking trigger at 13 TeV in LHC Run-2 and
new developments on standard and unconventional tracking signatures for
the upcoming LHC Run-3

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ABSTRACT

The performance of the Inner Detector tracking trigger of the ATLAS experiment at the LHC is presented for the data taking period of Run 2 (2015-2018). The Inner Detector tracking is used for the muon, electron, tau and b-jet triggers, and its high performance is essential for the ATLAS physics program such as precision measurements of the Standard Model and searches for new physics.

The application of Inner Detector tracking is being significantly expanded for Run 3. For the first time, full-detector tracking will be utilized for all signatures with jets and missing transverse momentum and dedicated triggers with unconventional tracking will be utilized to identify massive long-lived particles with displaced and disappearing track signatures. Several optimizations have been developed to meet computing resource limitations.

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1 Introduction

The ATLAS Inner Detector (ID) trigger runs tracking in order to enable the reconstruction of electrons, muons, taus, and b -jets for use in trigger decisions. For the Large Hadron Collider's (LHC) [1] Run 3, an expanded use of tracking is planned for jet, missing transverse momentum, and unconventional signatures. The ID trigger is a crucial element of the ATLAS trigger system to find and save events needed for the ATLAS physics program.

The ATLAS detector [2] is a multipurpose particle detector at the LHC with a forward-backward symmetric cylindrical geometry and a near 4π coverage in solid angle. It consists of an inner tracking detector surrounded by a thin superconducting solenoid providing a 2 T axial magnetic field, electromagnetic and hadronic calorimeters, and a muon spectrometer. The inner tracking detector covers the pseudorapidity range $|\eta| < 2.5$. It consists of silicon pixel (Pixel), silicon microstrip (SCT), and transition radiation tracking (TRT) detectors. An additional layer of silicon pixels, the insertable B-layer [3, 4], was installed before Run 2. Lead/liquid-argon (LAr) sampling calorimeters provide electromagnetic (EM) energy measurements with high granularity. A steel/scintillator-tile hadron calorimeter covers the central pseudorapidity range ($|\eta| < 1.7$). The endcap and forward regions are instrumented with LAr calorimeters for both the EM and hadronic energy measurements up to $|\eta| = 4.9$. The muon spectrometer surrounds the calorimeters and is based on three large superconducting air-core toroidal magnets with eight coils each. The field integral of the toroids ranges between 2.0 and 6.0 Tm across most of the detector. The muon spectrometer includes a system of precision chambers for tracking and fast detectors for triggering.

A two-level trigger system is used to select events. The first-level trigger is implemented in hardware and uses a subset of the detector information from the calorimeters and muon spectrometer to accept events at a rate below 100 kHz out of the 40 MHz collision rate. Small Regions-of-Interest (RoIs) around the calorimeter or muon spectrometer signatures are passed to the software-based High Level Trigger (HLT) that reduces the accepted event rate to 1 kHz on average depending on the data-taking conditions. The HLT uses offline-like reconstruction, including tracking, in order to determine which events to save. Tracking can be run over the entire ID (Full Scan) or in small RoIs, which vary in size but are of order 0.2 wide in pseudorapidity and azimuthal angle. An extensive software suite [5] is used in the reconstruction and analysis of real and simulated data, in detector operations, and in the trigger and data acquisition systems of the experiment.

2 Run 2 Inner Detector Trigger

The design and performance of the Run 2 ID trigger is described in detail in Ref. [6]. The tracking strategy was redesigned for Run 2 compared to Run 1, and the processing time, shown on the left of Figure 1, benefited from software optimizations. These changes resulted in a significant reduction in processing time, which was needed to meet computing requirements given the higher Run 2 average pile-up.

The tracking algorithms in the trigger start from the RoI, which may be the entire detector for Full Scan tracking. The data preparation step includes the retrieval of the hits from the SCT and Pixel detectors, clustering of those hits, and formation of space-points. The Fast Track Finder (FTF) runs the seeding and track formation. This step is unique to the trigger and is optimized for speed and efficiency with respect to the offline pattern recognition. Optionally, events may be discarded using this information in order to avoid unnecessary downstream processing. Finally, the precision tracking step runs offline-like track fitting, seeded by the spacepoints of the FTF tracks, by running the ambiguity removal tool. The purpose of the precision tracking step is to increase the purity and resolution of the tracks. Tracks are also extended into the TRT. Example Run 2 processing times for the main tracking steps for muons are shown on the right of Figure 1. The FTF performs the time consuming pattern recognition stage used to seed both the initial fast track fit used in the FTF itself and the full track fit performed by the precision tracking stage, which does not run its own pattern recognition. The tracking for isolation is significantly longer than the rest because it runs in a larger RoI and thus processes more data.

The ID tracking performed extremely well in Run 2 with high efficiencies for a variety of signatures. As an example, the efficiency for fast and precision tracking for electrons is shown on the left of Figure 2. The tracking is nearly fully efficient, with a small dip near the transition region between the barrel and end-cap

Figure 1: (left) Ambiguity resolution processing time before and after software optimizations, a newer GCC compiler, and the switch to the EIGEN library were implemented, as described in the text. (right) Run 2 processing time per muon RoI for the fast, precision, and isolation tracking steps [6].

of the ID. On the right of Figure 2 is the η resolution of muon tracks, demonstrating the improved resolution from running precision tracking on top of FTF.

Figure 2: (left) Efficiency for fast and precision tracking of electron candidates with respect to offline electrons. The small dips in efficiency around $|\eta| = 1.3$ correspond to the transition between the barrel and endcap of the Inner Detector. (right) Muon track η resolution with respect to offline muons for fast and precision tracking [6].

3 Faster Full-Detector Tracking for Run 3

A large increase in full detector tracking is planned for Run 3, but it is computationally expensive to run. Thus it was important to optimize Full Scan tracking in order to reduce the processing time. Several optimizations were implemented.

Forming seeds is one of the first steps of the tracking algorithm. Reducing the number of seeds decreases the time spent in the seeding step as well as downstream tracking steps as time is not wasted processing unnecessary seeds. Seeds are triplets of hits composed of two doublets sharing the middle hit. A machine learning based filter (Bayes classifier using a kernel density estimate) was developed to separate between doublets, pairs of hits, that will correctly be associated to a track and those that will not [7, 8]. The

classification is based on the polar angle θ of the doublets and the width of the pixel cluster w_η in η of the middle hit in the seed. The left of Figure 3 shows the predicted region of correct association to a track. The vertical structures are a result of training the classifier for Pixel barrel and end-cap doublets and standard and long pixel combinations. The area of predicted correct association is turned into a look-up-table in order to quickly evaluate if a doublet should be accepted. An operating point with a true positive rate of 95% was chosen, corresponding to roughly a factor of two reduction in the false positive rate. This reduction in bad seeds results in an overall speed up of $1.6\text{--}2.3\times$ for an average pile-up of 40–80, with a loss in efficiency of 0.7–1.0%. The right of Figure 3 shows the small loss in efficiency, mostly at larger $|\eta|$, compared to Monte Carlo truth tracks when enabling the filtering.

Figure 3: (left) Predicted classification of correct or incorrect hit association to a track for doublets from the Pixel detector based on the polar angle θ and cluster width w_η of the middle hit in a seed. (right) Efficiency versus truth track η with and without the machine learning based seed filtering [7].

A second optimization also targets the seeding for Full Scan tracking. By disabling the use of mixed seeds, those with both Pixel and SCT clusters, and using only seeds with three Pixel or three SCT clusters, the mean event processing time for the FTF step is reduced by a factor of 1.9 [9]. Using only Pixel or SCT seeds avoids the relatively large gap between the last Pixel layer and first SCT layer. The resulting loss in tracking efficiency is small, less than 1%, as shown on the right of Figure 4.

Figure 4: (left) Efficiency for Full Scan tracking both with and without seeds combining Pixel (P) and SCT (S) clusters. (right) Efficiency and normalized processing time for Full Scan tracking versus the z half-width of the tracking ROI. The standard deviation of the beam spot in z is indicated with vertical dotted lines [9].

A third optimization looks at the width of the RoI along the beam-line (z -axis). Restricting the size of the RoI in z reduces the processing time, while the efficiency of the tracking is largely unchanged for RoIs covering at least three standard deviations of the beam spot. The right of Figure 4 shows the slow decrease in efficiency for smaller RoIs, less than 1% decrease, while the processing time decreases by up to 30% for an RoI with a half width of roughly 130 mm.

4 Unconventional Tracking Triggers for Run 3

Long-lived particles (LLPs), those which do not immediately decay after production, result in a wide variety of discoverable signatures at the LHC. Thus they are an important part of the LHC's Run 3 physics program. Many of these unique signatures rely on tracking information in order to identify them, e.g. displaced vertices, jets, and leptons. During Run 2, only standard tracking was run in the trigger, with coverage in transverse impact parameter out to $|d_0| < 5\text{--}10$ mm, which is not viable for most LLP signatures. Run 2 searches generally relied on calorimeter and muons spectrometer based signatures to trigger events. These triggers had fairly high thresholds in order to keep the triggered event rate at a reasonable level, which reduced the acceptance of the trigger to LLP signatures. For Run 3, new triggers have been implemented to directly target events with disappearing tracks and displaced leptons.

Disappearing tracks result from the decay of a long-lived charged particle, for example a supersymmetric chargino, that traverses several inner layers of the ID, before decaying into invisible and low momentum particles. The low momentum particle is not tracked, so the signature in the detector is a short tracklet with a few hits on the inner silicon layers, which can not be extended into a full track. The FTF algorithm was modified in order to save tracklets that fail to become full tracks and is run in the Full Scan tracking used for the missing transverse momentum signatures. This signature has a large background, which makes it impracticable to trigger solely based on finding a tracklet. In order to reduce the background rate, a Boosted Decision Tree (BDT) was trained based on quantities such as the track parameters, quality of fit, and number of hits in the Pixel and SCT detectors. The performance of the BDT is shown on the left of Figure 5, with good separation between signal and background tracklets. Directly reconstructing the tracklet and reducing the background with the BDT allows for a lower missing transverse momentum threshold (80 GeV) compared to the default trigger (110 GeV), shown on the right of Figure 5. This results in a large increase in acceptance for models with lower momentum, e.g. roughly a factor of two for those with a transverse momentum of the chargino-chargino system of 100 GeV.

Figure 5: (left) The Boosted Decision Tree score used for separating signal-like disappearing track candidates (Monte Carlo) from background (Data). (right) Efficiency of the high level trigger to select simulated events with a long-lived chargino for the traditional missing transverse momentum trigger and the new disappearing track trigger, which allows for a lower missing transverse momentum threshold [10].

Run 2 searches for displaced leptons, for example Ref. [11], had limited acceptance in the trigger for events

with relatively low momentum electrons and muons. Models with long-lived supersymmetric staus with a mass around 100 GeV generally result in final state electrons and muons with momenta below the roughly 60 GeV thresholds needed to trigger the event. Further, the Run 2 triggers either required two objects in the event or had limited geometric acceptance. For the first time, Large Radius Tracking (LRT) [12] will be run in the trigger for Run 3 in order to reconstruct displaced tracks and directly trigger on displaced leptons. This is enabled by improvements to the algorithm [13] that reduce the number of fake tracks and reduce the processing time. The trigger runs LRT with the same configuration as the offline tracking, but still with the specialized FTF step with a different seeding algorithm. LRT can be run over the entire detector in a second pass after standard tracking on the remaining hits, as is done for offline LRT, or it can be run in RoIs as a single pass. The performance of the RoI-based LRT in terms of speed and efficiency was already sufficient without needing to complicate the algorithm. Primary differences compared to the standard tracking include using only SCT clusters for seeding, removing the ordering of seeds by impact parameter, and the tighter track selection introduced in the updated LRT configuration. Tracks are reconstructed for charged particles with a transverse momentum greater than 1 GeV and at least a small displacement of $|d_0| > 2$ mm; though, this is a soft cutoff in the case of the RoI tracking. For the Full Scan LRT, the removal of hits used for the standard tracking means there are essentially no real tracks left to reconstruct at low d_0 .

Figure 6: Efficiency of the muon (left) and electron (right) standard and large radius tracking high level triggers versus the decay radius of long-lived supersymmetric staus. The tracking used for the standard electron chain is limited to $|d_0| < 5$ mm, making the efficiency near zero by construction [14].

The efficiency of muon and electron LRT-based triggers is shown in Figure 6 versus the decay radius of long-lived supersymmetric staus, i.e. the radius at which the muons or electrons are produced. The standard tracking based trigger's efficiency falls off rapidly, and the large radius tracking based trigger recovers the efficiency out to 300 mm, the first layer of the SCT. The LRT requires eight hits on the track, so the efficiency falls off rapidly past 300 mm. The hit requirement means that for very displaced or non-pointing tracks, the inner most hits on the track may fall outside of the RoI acceptance in the azimuthal angle ϕ , limiting the ability to reconstruct such tracks. The diagram in the left of Figure 7 depicts this. The RoI is approximately a wedge originating from the origin in the $r - \phi$ plane, with some fixed opening angle in ϕ . Generally, the processing time for the LRT in RoIs is faster than for the standard lepton triggers. The thresholds of the displaced lepton triggers for Run 3 are near those of the prompt lepton triggers, approximately 25 GeV. These are well below the thresholds from Run 2 and only require a single particle to pass the trigger, resulting in a large increase in acceptance for models with relatively low momentum displaced leptons in Run 3.

The Full Scan LRT trigger may be useful for signatures without an obvious RoI, or to add LRT to all of the jets in an event. It is not in the trigger menu at the time of writing, but is used in the development of displaced jet and vertex triggers that may be included in later trigger menus. The right plot of Figure 7 shows the efficiency of the Full Scan LRT for tracks from a displaced R-hadron decay (decaying into a muon

and quark) versus its decay radius. As with the RoI case, the LRT recovers the efficiency out to large radii compared to the standard tracking. The Full Scan tracking needs to process a large number of seeds, resulting in a longer processing time relative to the standard tracking. Optimizations to reduce the processing time result in a reduced efficiency compared to the offline tracking.

Figure 7: (left) Sketch in the $R-\phi$ plane of a very displaced track (thick-dashed line) where the first hit (solid dot) is missed in the online tracking due to falling outside of the Region-of-Interest's azimuthal acceptance. This is overlaid on a depiction of a track passing through detector layers [15]. (right) Efficiency to reconstruct tracks from a displaced R-hadron (decaying into a muon and quark) versus its decay radius for the high level trigger standard and large radius tracking as well as the offline tracking [14].

5 Conclusions

The Inner Detector Trigger is a vital part of the ATLAS trigger system, which supports the ATLAS physics program. It performed extremely well during the LHC's Run 2, with a high efficiency with respect to the offline tracking. An expanded use of Full Scan tracking in jet and missing transverse momentum triggers is anticipated for Run 3, and several optimizations have resulted in large reductions in the mean event processing time due to the tracking. Triggers targeting long-lived particles making use of unconventional tracking, such as large radius tracking and reconstructing short tracklets, have been developed for Run 3. The new triggers greatly increase the acceptance of the trigger to models with long-lived particles compared to what was possible in Run 2, particularly for those scenarios with relatively low momentum particles (below roughly 60 GeV).

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